

Short-term health co-benefits of existing climate policies: the need for more ambitious and integrated policy action

Climate change and air pollution are two interconnected major risks for human health.¹ The sources of greenhouse gases—namely, the combustion of fossil fuels—are the main sources of harmful air pollution. The literature has extensively analysed the health co-benefits of lowered air pollution associated with alternative decarbonisation strategies.^{2,3} However, these studies have been focused on stylised or cost-optimal scenarios with long-term optimistic and uncertain assumptions about future mitigation efforts. The 2021 United Nations Climate Change Conference in Glasgow increased the ambition for the 2030 emission reduction targets compared with the 2015 pledges, and several countries presented their commitment to achieve net zero emissions by the second half of the century. Nevertheless, there are several alternative strategies to achieve net zero economies, which would result in very different emission pathways.⁴

Considering the uncertainty in the beyond 2030 decarbonisation plans and given that emission reduction policies are mainly defined up to 2030, we estimated the health co-benefits up to 2030 attributable to ambient air pollution reductions associated with existing climate policies and pledges (ie, nationally determined contributions) for the world at a regional level. We first calculated the health co-benefits of the implementation of the current portfolio of emission reduction policies, such as renewable energy shares, vehicle fuel standards, and energy efficiency targets, for all G20 countries. We then estimated the co-benefits for a second scenario, in which the post-Glasgow emission reduction targets are implemented on top of existing policies. The scenarios include all the climate policies and emissions targets submitted or announced by June, 2022. If, in any region, current policies already achieve the nationally determined contributions target, no additional emission constraint is applied. On the other hand, in regions where the existing climate policies are not sufficient to achieve the mitigation target in the nationally determined contributions, the model endogenously estimates a regional carbon tax to achieve the nationally determined contributions based on the least cost approach. Van de Ven and

colleagues provide a full description of these scenarios, with a complete list of the implemented policies and emission targets.⁵

For calculations of the health co-benefits, we combine the Global Change Analysis Model (GCAM)⁶ with rfasst,⁷ a tool designed to calculate a range of adverse health and agricultural effects attributable to air pollution for alternative scenarios. Greenhouse gases and air pollutant emission pathways are projected by GCAM and fed into rfasst, which calculates a range of health impacts attributable to both fine particulate matter (ie, PM_{2.5}) and ozone exposure. In contrast to other studies that use a single health impact function, we used a combination of existing risk functions, including integrated exposure–response functions from the Global Burden of Diseases, Injuries, and Risk Factors Study,⁸ Burnett and colleagues,⁹ and Jerret and colleagues,¹⁰ and the Global Exposure Mortality Model¹¹ (including and excluding the Chinese cohort that covers much of the exposure distribution; appendix).

See Online for appendix

We found that global premature mortality associated with ambient air pollution will reduce in the short term (up to 2030), accounting for 166 623 (lower and upper bounds obtained by combining lower and upper parameters within the health impact functions: 72 789–260 347) avoided deaths per year worldwide due to existing climate policies, and 361 744 (151 698–571 779) avoided deaths per year worldwide due to the implementation of updated nationally determined contributions on top of current policies. Thus, the additional contribution of the nationally determined contributions is of the order of 195 121 avoided deaths per year. Although the contribution of both the current policies and climate pledges is a positive co-benefit, we estimate that there will still be 5.5 million (2.77–8.23) premature mortalities attributable to exposure to both PM_{2.5} and ozone in 2030 globally. Hence, avoided premature mortalities associated with current policies and pledges are relatively small, representing around 2.6–3.2% for climate policies, and 5.2–6.5% with the addition of nationally determined contributions.

Regionally, we found that the regions that benefit the most from the implementation of the existing climate

policy portfolio are central Europe and China, which have 80 avoided premature deaths per million people and 69 avoided premature deaths per million people, respectively. Health co-benefits in other regions are substantially smaller, and in some regions (eg, South Korea) premature mortalities could even be increased compared with baseline, due to the increase in biomass for electricity generation and the subsequent increase in organic carbon emissions. In the climate policies and national determined contributions scenario, avoided premature mortalities per million people are larger in all regions, and heavily concentrated in Central Asia (148 avoided premature mortalities per million people), China (100 avoided premature mortalities per million people), Central Europe (98 avoided premature mortalities per million people), and India (77 avoided premature mortalities per million people).

In summary, health co-benefits associated with current policies and nationally determined contributions are relatively small. The results show that to reduce health impacts attributable to ambient air pollution rapidly, additional policy action that is explicitly designed for tackling air pollutant emissions will be needed. First, emissions per unit of activity should be urgently reduced through technological progress (eg, flue-gas desulphurisation) and more stringent emission controls and regulation. In our projections, emission factors for the alternative pollutants moderately decrease over time in all the scenarios, following the central trends in existing literature. Having faster and more pronounced decreases, particularly in the most affected regions, will produce direct health co-benefits. In addition, disentangling climate action from air pollution can create additional hazards for human health. The large-scale deployment of low-carbon technologies, such as biomass or carbon capture and storage, although effectively reducing greenhouse gas emissions, will not

decrease the emissions of harmful air pollutants (eg, nitrogen oxides and organic carbon), which highlights the need to integrate human health considerations into climate policy making.¹²

We declare no competing interests.

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